

NON-VERBAL EXPRESSION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK GREETING

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Annotation: This article illustrates non-verbal expressions of respect in English and Uzbek communication and compares with some examples. Studying these expressions helps us to understand and compare English speaking countries non-verbal language with ours. Cause they have significant difference from each other. To know non-verbal expressions gives an opportunity to understand people's ideas much more clearly and to act according to it.

Key words: respect, expression, non-verbal communication, culture, difference.

Introduction.

Nonverbal communication, we can call it as manual language also, means the process of sending and receiving messages without words and consuming the data which are sent by the movements of the body. Nonverbal communication refers to the ways in which beings convey information about their emotions, needs, intentions, attitudes and thoughts without utilizing any means of verbal communication including words. Nonverbal expressions play very important role in human's life as we can not express our ideas very clearly and vividly. These actions contain expressing emotions; conveying interpersonal attitudes like friendliness, insult or dominance over somebody; respect or disrespect; regulating effect; ruling turn taking between people in conversation. Cultural, gender, and other group differences in nonverbal behaviour have been documented as well as individual differences in usage and in the accuracy of nonverbal transmission and reception.

Nonverbal communication is expressed through nonlinguistic suggests it's the actions or attributes of humans, together with their look, use of objects, sound, time, smell and space that have socially shared its own significance and stimulate that means in others. It includes visual (kinesic) cues like facial expressions, eye movements, gestures and body orientation; vocal (paralinguistic) cues like volume, pitch, rate and inflection; proxemic cues like area and distance; modality or smell cues; cues provided

by unit communication and appearance; cues sent through color; and chronemic or time cues. Although we tend to might send nonverbal messages on purpose or by accident, their meaning relies on how they are received and understood.

As a result we can portray that these types of messages fulfill metacommunicative functions, clarifying both the nature of our relationship, the meaning of our verbal messages. In fact, researchers conclude that nonverbal cues carry approximately two-thirds of a message`s communicative value. Even when used independently of words as long as an observer derives meaning from them, nonverbal messages increase the communication volume and importance.

Furthermore, many scientists conclude that nonverbal cues carry just about simple fraction of a message`s communicative value which is received and replied according to meaning. The ability to comprehend of nonverbal expressions helps to open the door to the real meaning. People make use of various nonverbal expressions in everyday life regardless of their culture. There are also various commonly used nonverbal expressions in Uzbek culture, including nodding to approve and agree with something, shaking index finger to warn someone, clapping to praise somebody and also showing thumb up to mean something is great, perfect and worth.

One of the similar features of Uzbek and English is the way of greeting between man and man who shake hands while greeting each other. However, generally asking loads of questions, such as about family, work, health during the greeting is typical of Uzbek people from the point of politeness and no detailed response for every question is accepted as a normal case that does not occur in the same way as English greeting. In addition, according to Uzbek culture, women greeting women, the older ones may grip an arm of each other. Friends and family members exchange kisses on the cheek and hugs each other. In England, the first meeting between women are generally done by shaking hands.

In Uzbekistan, greeting between men and women may involve only saying “Assalomu alaykum”, sometimes exchanging a nod. One of the distinguishing feature of Uzbek people is that there is no touch by people of the opposite gender, while it is normal by family members. As Uzbekistan is a Muslim country, both men and women do not touch with one another. Therefore, most men and women do not prefer a handshake. Nevertheless, a handshake is a form of greeting between men and women in England. Also, it is women who tend to extend their hand first.

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